

MICROSTRUCTURAL STUDIES OF δ -ALUMINA FIBRE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM AND Al ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

The tensile and impact properties have been investigated of composites of short δ -alumina fibres in matrices of nominally pure Al, commercially pure Al and an Al-2.5%Mg alloy. Failure strains of up to 3.8% in combination with significant strengthening were observed. Microstructural study of fractured specimens indicated that further improvement in ductility might be achieved by optimization of fibre morphology.

INTRODUCTION

Al-alloy matrix composites, prepared by pressure-assisted melt infiltration of preforms of non-continuous alumina fibres, have been established as a promising group of metal matrix composites for engineering applications (see e.g. 1-3). A major drawback of these materials is their poor ductility and toughness; their elongation to fracture, for example, seldom exceeds 3%. The present work is an investigation of the fracture properties of selected examples of such composites, being a preparatory study within a programme planned to give a clearer understanding of their mechanical behaviour. A question to be answered is to what extent the toughness is determined by such factors as matrix microstructure, the fibre/matrix interface and the fibre morphology (fibre dimensions, orientation, spatial distribution, etc.).

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

Composites were prepared with δ -alumina fibres (ICI Saffil RF-grade) in three different matrices viz: high-purity Al (99.99%) (0.0008 wt% Fe, 0.0013 wt% Si, 0.0007 wt% Mg, 0.0024 wt% Cu, 0.0007 wt% Mg, hereinafter referred to as HP), commercial purity Al (CP) containing in the as-supplied condition 0.22 wt% Fe, 0.13 wt% Si, 0.01 wt% Mn, 0.02 wt% Zn, and an Al-2.5%Mg alloy containing in the as supplied condition 2.3 wt% Mg, 0.30 wt% Fe, 0.21 wt% Si, 0.3 wt% Mn, 0.03 wt% Zn. The fibres were received in the form of 5 and 20 vol.% preform discs of diameter 120 mm and height 20 mm. They contained about 5 wt.% silica binder. The properties of the fibres (4) and details of the preform structure (5) have been given elsewhere.

2. Composite preparation

The composites were prepared by squeeze casting using an inverted, cylindrical, heated die arrangement. The matrix was melted and held in a separate furnace. A measured quantity was transferred to the system immediately before casting. The preforms, cut to discs of 100 mm diameter, fitted the die

closely. The infiltration speed was around 30 mm/s and the final pressure, maintained during solidification was 50 MPa. Process variables were melt temperature (T_m), preform pre-heat temperature (T_p), and die temperature (T_D). In general these were kept as low as possible without loss of composite quality as assessed in terms of adequate infiltration (see below). The temperature of the preform and melt were not measured directly during infiltration but are estimated to lie in the range of 600-650 °C, depending on T_p and T_m . The investigated composites, with corresponding values of process variables and chemical analysis are included in Table 1. High process temperatures are reflected by higher Fe and Si contents in the matrix.

Table 1. Process temperatures and in situ chemical composition of matrix.

Composite (matrix)	Vol.% fibres	Temperature (°C)			Chemical composition (wt.%)			
		T_m	T_p	T_D	Si	Mg	Fe	Mn
HP Al (1)	20	899	800	310	0.093	0.002	0.021	0.001
HP Al (2)	20	1050	900	440	0.10	0.001	0.17	0.003
CP Al	5	840	840	500	0.13	0.01	0.22	0.01
CP Al (1)	20	850	850	487	0.53	0.003	0.43	0.1
CP Al (2)	20	905	900	330	0.51	0.007	0.44	0.064
Al-Mg	5	1050	700	410	-	-	-	-
Al-Mg	20	960	700	400	0.59	1.30	0.28	0.26

3. Mechanical Testing

Tensile tests were performed at room temperature on cylindrical specimens of 6.4 mm diameter and 25 mm gauge length, taken from the cast discs with their axes parallel and close to the disc diameter. The tests were made at a crosshead speed of 0.48 mm/s in a screw driven testing machine, the strain being measured with a clip-on strain gauge. Instrumented, V-notch Charpy impact tests were carried out at room temperature on bars with dimensions 5 x 10 x 50 mm. These were cut such that their fracture plane lay parallel to the cylindrical axis of the disc. At least three samples from each casting were tested.

4. Metallography and Fractography

As-cast and tensile tested samples were sectioned and prepared for metallographic examination using standard grinding and diamond polishing techniques. The polished surfaces were examined unetched and etched with both optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Detailed microanalysis with transmission electron microscopy and scanning Auger microscopy are described elsewhere (6,7). To estimate matrix grain size, as-cast samples were anodise-etched using Barker's reagent (4 ml HBF₄ (48%), 200 ml H₂O at 20 V).

To best reveal phenomena such as poor infiltration, microporosity, fibre damage etc, a deep electropolishing technique was developed. This involved electropolishing the mechanically polished surface using a solution of 4.7% perchloric acid, 10% 2-butoxyethanol, 82% ethanol and H₂O at 12-20 V for 1-2 s. This polished down the matrix, removing smeared out material but leaving fibres, binder and intermetallic phases. The method was used for example to judge the effectiveness of infiltration (Figs. 1 and 2) and in a quantitative measurement of fibre fracture in axial sections of tensile tested specimens. In the latter study the number of fractures per unit area were counted at a magnification of 780X in narrow bands (0.15 mm wide) across the section at selected distances from the fracture surface. A total surface area of 0.50 mm² at each distance was counted. At the fracture surface the count was made in a band following the surface profile. The fracture surfaces of the tensile and impact specimens were examined qualitatively using SEM.

Figure 1. Incomplete infiltration of a 20% HP Al composite. Specimen is polished and deep etched.

Figure 2. Complete infiltration of a 5% HP Al composite. Note: a) intermetallics, b) SiO₂-binder.

RESULTS

1. General Microstructure

The fibre morphology (spatial uniformity and orientation distribution) of composites prepared with preforms of the same batch as those used here, has been described in detail earlier (5); the morphology of the present composites appeared to be very similar. Infiltration and wetting of the fibres was effective (Fig. 2). The CP and Al-Mg matrices contained small amounts of second phases in the form of interdendritic eutectics (Figs. 3 and 4). In the CP matrices they were largely Al-Fe-Si intermetallics (6). In the Al-Mg composites, apart from the occurrence of a dual eutectic consisting of Al-Fe-Si and Mg₂Si, Mg had segregated to the fibre/matrix interface, apparently attracted through reaction with the silica binder to form Mg₂Si (7). The grains were columnar with a width of 0.1 mm and 1 to 6 mm length.

2. Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the composites together with those of unreinforced matrix are collected in Table 2. The CP and Al-Mg composites exhibited significant ductility in tensile failure, the 20 vol.% Al-Mg sample showing a small but distinct tendency to neck. The HP composites were more brittle. Macroscopically the 20 vol.% CP and Al-Mg composites failed in a shear mode, while the 20 vol.% HP and 5 vol.% Al-Mg composites failed in a cup and cone manner. The HP Al specimen 2 broke at the shoulder. The impact behaviour of both the HP and CP composites was brittle although

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the tested composites.

Composite matrix	fibre vol.%	Tensile Properties			Impact Energy Charpy V kJ/m ²
		Yield stress MPa	UTS MPa	Fracture strain %	
HP Al (1)	20	68	124	1.4	41
HP Al (2)	20	108	155	0.4	22
CP Al	0	-	-	-	> 370
CP Al	5	-	-	-	50
CP Al (1)	20	69	141	3.2	65
CP Al (2)	20	87	205	3.6	36
Al-Mg	0	-	(175)	-	-
Al-Mg	5	99	200	3.5	-
Al-Mg	20	110	230	3.9	-

Figure 3. SEM-micrograph of a CP composite. Note the eutectic AlFeSi intermetallics.

Figure 4. SEM-micrograph of an Al-Mg composite. Note Mg₂Si (black) and AlFeSi intermetallic (bright).

the observed differences in fracture energy values, ie higher for CP material is judged to be significant.

Little difference could be seen between the fracture surfaces of tensile and impact specimens except that the impact surfaces were macroscopically smoother. Not unexpectedly, many transverse fibres could be seen in all the fracture surfaces. In the CP and the Al-Mg composites (Fig 6.) the surfaces of these fibres exhibited much adherent matrix on them. Moreover, there were many examples of longitudinally split fibres. The dimples centred around axially-oriented fibres were generally quite deep and the fibres exhibited relatively little pull-out or debonding. In contrast, in the HP composite fracture surfaces (Fig 5.) the transverse fibres were usually very clean and fibre splitting was rare. The dimples around axial fibres were shallower and debonding was frequently observed. All these observations indicate that the fibre matrix bonding was significantly weaker in the HP composites. A schematic interpretation of the difference in dimple formation is given in Fig 7.

Figure 5. Tensile test fracture surface of an HP composite.

Figure 6. Tensile test fracture surface of a CP composite.

Figure 7. Schematic interpretation of dimple formation in a) well bonded composite (CP and Al-Mg) and b) poorly bonded composite (HP).

3. Fiber Fracture

Significant fibre fracture was observed in axial sections of the tensile test specimens. The fractures were mainly transverse failures of fibres with axial or near-axial orientations. Fig. 8 shows the extent of fibre fracture as a function of distance from the fracture surfaces of selected specimens. It is to be noted that, comparing the different samples at a given distance from the fracture surface, there is a small but significant, increase in fibre fracture density with increasing strain to failure of the composite. Similarly there is an increase in fracture frequency towards the fracture surface; this is most marked for the Al-Mg matrix. The increase in crack density was due not only to an increase in the number of fractures in axially oriented fibres but also to a broadening of the range of orientation of off-axis fibres suffering fracture, extending even to transverse fibres ie fibre splitting (Fig. 9). The standard deviation in the crack density values was high viz around 100 %. this was mainly the consequence of fibre bundling causing grouping of cracks (Fig. 10). Considerable cavity formation occurred particularly in the CP and Al-Mg composites, around both transverse fibres and the fibre fractures (Fig. 11). Only one example of a large matrix cavity was observed; this was close to the fracture surface of the Al-Mg sample.

Figure 8. Crack density versus the distance from the fracture surface.

Figure 9. SEM-micrograph showing transverse fibre splitting. Note: Cu (white spots) from the bakelite mount is precipitated on the matrix surface during the electro-polishing.

Figure 10. SEM-micrograph showing bundled cracks and multiple fracture.

Figure 11. SEM-micrograph showing cavity formation near the fracture surface of a tensile specimen. Specimen is cut longitudinally, polished and electro-polished for 1 sec.

DISCUSSION

Measurement of the fibre orientation distribution shows that less than 5% of the fibres lie within $\pm 10^\circ$ of the tensile axis (5). This represents less than 1 vol.% of the composites and must therefore lie well below the minimum fraction required to give load transfer reinforcement of the fracture strength. This is confirmed by the observation of multiple fracture of the fibres. The composite strength and ductility is then determined by the matrix which indeed is one necessary condition for the achievement of a ductile composite. Nevertheless, strength reinforcement was achieved in all the composites. This can be partly attributed to dislocation hardening mechanisms and partly to constraint of matrix deformation by fibres. It should nevertheless be remembered that, prior to fracture, non-oriented fibres and fibres of sub-critical length can also provide some load-transfer strengthening. The observed increase in fibre fracture density with the level of strain in the surrounding composite can be explained by strain hardening of the matrix. Final failure of the composite occurs by linking of matrix cavities around these cracks and around debonded transverse fibres. The fractographic and metallographic studies indicate that the fibre matrix bonding was greater in the CP and Al-Mg composites than in the HP composites, thereby imparting a greater tolerance towards fibre fracture and cavity formation in them and thus contributing to their relatively high ductility. It is noteworthy that the improved bonding seemingly outweighs any negative effects caused by the presence of intermetallics and interfacial reaction products in these matrices. It may be speculated that to achieve best ductility there exists an optimum interfacial strength since some debonding would help to relieve matrix constraint. Similarly, optimisation of the fibre morphology ie orientation distribution, aspect ratio and spatial uniformity can be expected to lead to further improvements in ductility. The lower ductility of the HP-matrix composites in the present study is attributed to a poorer interfacial bonding.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank civ. ing. Magnus Levin and staff of the Swedish National Testing Institute for expert help and equipment for impact testing. We are also indebted to AluminiumTeknik (Gränges) for supply of Al and for performance of chemical analysis. This work was financed by the Swedish Board of Technical Development (STU).

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